

FOREIGN ECONOMIC RELATIONS IN THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

Jumayev Samariddin O'ktamovich

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami
4th grade student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10682353>

Keywords: independence, stages, agreements, cooperation agreements, commonwealth states, resources

Introduction: Uzbekistan has for some time been perceived by the world because of its geostrategic position, underground assets, essentially because of the difficult work and ability of the Uzbek public. Our nation has been helped by companions, yet in addition has well established participation relations with a few nations. Our lovely and rich land pulled in various trespassers with these wealth. Throughout the last centuries, our nation has been attacked a few times. Alexander the Incomparable's phalanxes, Middle Easterners, Genghis Khan's soldiers visited here, and toward the finish of the nineteenth 100 years, Russia attacked, and the pioneer system, including the Soviet system, went on for in excess of 100 years. After every attack, our kin recaptured their autonomy, and presently, as in the past, the brilliant day of the freedom occasion has come - August 31, 1991, and presently it is perpetually, for eternity.

Free advancement infers the required passage of an autonomous state into the world political framework. Uzbekistan's regular longing to reinforce its power by presenting it as an undeniable individual from the world framework comes from this. On the edge of the 21st 100 years somewhat recently, the social and political circumstance on the planet has changed fundamentally. Somewhat recently of the twentieth hundred years, the governmental issues of the "position of solidarity" was supplanted by the governmental issues of levelheaded common discourse.

In spite of being a moderately youthful free country, Uzbekistan has started to assume a significant part on the planet political field. New possibilities for the improvement of all humanity have showed up, tremendous changes have occurred in the field of correspondence, and the further advancement of worldwide relations altogether affects human existence. At the point when the cycles of mix and individuals' craving to bring together have escalated, the need to safeguard public qualities and otherworldly legacy has emerged by leading a free strategy.

Because of its geological and political position, Uzbekistan has assumed a commendable position on the planet local area. This is affirmed by:

1. Uzbekistan has a good topographical and political position, as it has the most extravagant energy assets in Focal Asia and a wide transportation organization.

2. Most of the number of inhabitants in the Focal Asian district lives in Uzbekistan. The logical and specialized capability of Uzbekistan is higher than the logical and specialized capability of adjoining nations.

On Walk 2, 1992, the Republic of Uzbekistan turned into a full individual from the Unified Countries without precedent for its set of experiences. Uzbekistan stepped up to the plate and make a super durable body that would zero in on issues, for example, dependability and security in the Focal Asian locale, clashes in Tajikistan and Afghanistan, the battle against drug dealing, and the natural emergency of the island.

With the backing of the drive of the Leader of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in February 1993, the delegate office of the UN in Uzbekistan was opened in Tashkent. There are likewise various parts of the UN in our country (the High Chief for Evacuees, the World Wellbeing Association, the Kids' Asset, and so on.).

The Republic of Uzbekistan is an individual from various lofty global associations in the fields of economy, science, innovation and culture (World Bank, Global Financial Asset, European Bank for Remaking and Improvement, Global Olympic Panel, and so on.). As a free country, Uzbekistan has marked various shows and conventions of the UN, OSCE and CIS. Lately, Uzbekistan has zeroed in its international strategy on the turn of events and reinforcing of relations with cutting edge created nations. Close participation with the USA, Germany, France, Italy, Extraordinary England, Japan, South Korea, Turkey and other created nations started to prove to be fruitful. Another thing in international strategy was the settlement of everlasting kinship with Turkey.

Toward the finish of April 1993, the Leader of Uzbekistan paid an authority visit to Germany. Islam Karimov met with German Chancellor Helmut Kohl. The gatherings consented to commonly useful arrangements on social trade, examined issues of venture, directing joint logical exploration, and consented to lay out an extraordinary asset to help scholarly potential. The appointment of Uzbekistan got to know the modern creation of Germany. The visit was compelling and made a strong starting point for future participation.

What's more, on June 9-12, 1994, the State appointment of Uzbekistan visited the Netherlands, where it held chats with Sovereign Beatrix and State head Rudolph Loafers. The individuals from the assignment of Uzbekistan visited ranches having some expertise in horticulture and animal cultivation.

Toward the finish of the visit, a respective convention on exchange and financial participation and a joint assertion on the standards of collaboration between the two nations were agreed upon. The gatherings consented to supply Uzbekistan with cutting edge present day farming advances, seeds and rearing steers.

Conclusion

By and large, unfamiliar monetary relations became significant in guaranteeing development and improvement during the long stretches of autonomy. Through collaboration, economic accords, speculation valuable open doors and mechanical trade, nations have succeeded on the planet economy. Uzbekistan has likewise gone through numerous troublesome stages during these periods. However, today it is viewed as one of the nations with its own power.

References:

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Together we will build a free and prosperous, democratic country of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, Publishing House of Uzbekistan, 2016.
2. Mirziyoev Sh.m. We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people. Tashkent, Publishing House of Uzbekistan, 2017.
3. Bakiev, A., & Yuldasheva, Z. (2020). The fifth representative of the Ancient East. Theoretical and applied sciences, (8), 39-45
4. Allamuratov Sh.A. Istoriya Amudarinskogo sudostroeniya bulletin is scientific and practical. 2020. T. 6. # 10. P. 422-429.
5. Tursunov nn, Allamuratov Sh.A. Development of trade relations and crafts in Vostochnoy Bukary // science and practice bulletin. 2021. T.7. # 3. P. 348-353.

